

The Impact of Socio-Economic Development and Wellbeing of Asian Economy

Trisha Rahman¹

¹Department Business Management and Economics, Liaoning University of Technology, China

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*Corresponding Author:

Trisha Rahman,

rahman.trisha.bd@gmail.com

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to assess the effect of Utility on Socio-economic acceleration in Asia based on 52 countries/territories, while the effects of other variables that are also assumed to affect Socio-economic acceleration are statistically controlled. For this purpose, this study explores different patterns of Socio-economic acceleration based on 18 'Socio-economic' variables, including the Utility. There are six patterns of Socio-economic acceleration identified: (1) Utility-driven; (2) export-led; (3) oil-rich; (4) savings-based; (5) government (public) spending-based and (6) domestic financing-based. Empirical evidences show that the dominance of the Utility-driven Socio-economic acceleration in Asia cannot be denied. The patterns found in Asia are shared with the rest of the world economy, yet there were some 'uniqueness' to the Asian patterns, which feature as follows: (1) high savings; (2) a large defense spending affected by both oil-richness and politics (authoritarian government); and (3) high 'national' global competitiveness worldwide. And any negative 'uniqueness' to the Asian economy should be reassessed in light of the 'multidimensionality' of successful Utility-driven Socio-economic acceleration model as empirically proven in Asia.

Keywords: Utility; Driven economy; Uniqueness to Asian economy; Export-led economy; Oil-rich economy; Factor analysis

Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to assess the effect of Utility on Socio-economic acceleration in Asia based on 52 countries. It assesses the effect of the consumer-spending/Utility on Socio-economic acceleration while so many other theories of Socio-economic acceleration and variables thereof such as financing, export/trade, savings, oil, defense spending, for examples, are controlled. Many theories of Socio-economic acceleration are based on a single variable either as a cause of Socio-economic acceleration (GDP/PPP) or as a variable to assess its

effect on t quality of life. This univariate approach coalesced on a single-variable fail to identify a genuine 'independent' effect of an individual single variable on Socio-economic acceleration. Can Socio-economic acceleration in Asia be driven by consumer spending/Utility? What can be t effect of consumer-spending on Socio-economic acceleration independent of savings, export, financing (foreign direct financing or domestic financing), and innovation, for examples? Can a Utility-driven economy replace financing or export-driven economy? How are different theories of Socio-economic development with their respective variable(s) correlated with each other? How can such theories and variables be grouped and patterned according to their similarities or differences" T groupings and t correlations (causal or relational) between/among t variables will be t major parts of t patterns of Socio-economic acceleration that this study aims to explore in t Asian economy.

Materials and methods

Many theories and variables thereof are assumed to affect Socio-economic acceleration. Utility is one of tm/Consumer spending is t amount of money spent by individuals or households in an economy. Utility is a major acceleration engine. One of t ways to determine how much Socio-economic acceleration is accomplished is to measure t GDP (Gross Domestic Product). T GDP is based on t following formula: $GDP=C+I+G+NX$, were C=Consumer spending; I=Business financings; G=Government spending; NX=Net exports. T equation indicates that t consumer spending is a vital part of Socio-economic acceleration along with capital financings (both foreign direct financing/FDI and domestic private financing), government spending, and trade (net export). Supply-side Socio-economics is a macro economic theory, explaining that Socio-economic acceleration can be most effective Level\ created by investing in capital and by lowering barriers on t manufacturing of goods and services. Consumers will benefit from a greater supply of goods and services at lower prices. The financing and expansion of businesses will increase t demand for employees and therefore create jobs, which also mean to increase in consumer-spending. Typical policy recommendations of supply-side economists are lower marginal tax rates and less government regulation. Financing, particularly foreign direct financing (FDI) in flow, does increase Socio-economic development of t recipient countries. This is particularly notable in developing countries were multinational corporations (MNCs) via their respective FDI are doing their businesses. A high rate of financing in t present make possible future consumer spending. A number of economists have emphasized physical financing: that is, the accumulation of structures, machinery, business plant and equipment and other tangible assets [1]. Gary [2] has emphasized t accumulation of human capital. Even physical financing is not possible or effective without t human capital. Globalization does affect Socio-economic acceleration and development. re are pros and cons of t role of globalization in enhancing Socio-economic acceleration and quality of life. Stiglitz [3] was critical of globalization, as it has deepened global inequality between t haves and have-nots,

especially in the less developed countries. Yet Goklany [4] argued for a positive effect of Socio-economic globalization via free trade, which helped to enhance human well-being. In export-driven Socio-economic acceleration, terms of trade (export and import) does affect Socio-economic acceleration. Terms of trade, favorable or unfavorable, could affect Socio-economic development. A favorable term of trade, which is based on an increase in export prices relative to import prices, allows a larger volume of imports to be purchased with a given volume of exports. Thus, the favorable terms of trade imply an increase in the real purchasing power of domestic manufacturing, which is equivalent to a transfer of income from the rest of the world. Terms of trade can have large impacts on Utility, savings, and financing as well. On the other hand, unfavorable terms of trade will result in a negative or low Socio-economic acceleration particularly in developing countries, as they rely on the export of a single or a few primary commodities [5, 6]. Export-led acceleration is a trade and Socio-economic policy aiming to speed up the industrialization process of a country by exporting goods. During 1970 and 80s, the export-oriented industrialization was particularly characteristic of the development of the national economies of the Asian Tigers/Dragons: Hong Kong, South Korea, Taiwan, and Singapore.

1 Types of political system affect the quality of life. Democratic political system with a 'free' market-economy (Socio-economic freedom) as well as with a higher degree of political freedom enhances the quality of life. Russett [7] found that democracies reflect in political freedom, are efficient in generating wealth and Socio-economic acceleration. Many developing countries have implemented liberal Socio-economic reforms in recent decades. They have been successful in Socio-economic acceleration (e.g., Chile, Brazil, etc.), yet there are still many other developing countries that remain poor and have not experienced any sufficient Socio-economic acceleration. While political liberalizations and reforms, with minimal corruption, are required for a sustainable Socio-economic acceleration, China and Singapore, for examples, with their respective 'authoritarian capitalism' have still documented a rapid Socio-economic acceleration without undertaking sufficient political liberalization. South Korea was able to rapidly develop in the 1970s and 80s while its political system still remained authoritarian. Although income distribution, equal or unequal, is affected by ethnicity, gender, or geographic region, Clemens [8] nevertheless argues that a stronger role for the state (i.e., authoritarian political system) is advantageous for equal distribution of income. And the most vulnerable members of societies can be safeguarded by the role of a stronger authoritarian government. Stiglitz [3] argues that policies based on the Washington Consensus produce disappointing results as they are anchored in a free-market dogma, which ignores the unique socio-cultural contexts of countries where they are applied. The G20 group of governments agreed in 2010 on a 'new' Seoul Development Consensus. In contrast with the 'older' Washington Consensus, the Seoul Consensus allows a larger role for state intervention. Rather than seeking to impose a uniform top-down solution, the Seoul Consensus postulates that solutions should be tailored to the requirements of individual developing countries.

2. An excessive defense spending disproportionate to Socio-economic capacity siphons oil resources, which otherwise could have been used for Socio-economic development.

Methodology

The following 18 variables below were selected. The study is a cross national comparative analysis of 52 countries in Asia. The data cover the 2012-2016 periods. Countries have different time/year for their respective data availability for each of the 18 variables during the period covered. Fifty-two (52) countries/territories in Asia are used in this analysis. The cross-national (cross-sectional) comparative analysis does merit the followings. First, the benefit of a cross-sectional study design is that it allows researchers to compare many different variables at the same period of time. Since so many variables across the 52 countries in Asia are used in this study, the longitudinal analysis amenable to a few variables for a longer period of time cannot be a suitable design for this study. Second, cross-sectional studies based on many cases (countries) as well as on many variables across the countries can also sort out causal relations between the variables via statistical control, such as regression or factor analyses, for examples. The non-experimental cross-sectional design, like an experimental design, can still establish causal relations between variables via the statistical, not experimental, control. Based on the review of literature and theories, the following 18 variables were selected. Each of the 18 variables is operationalized/ measured as follows:

1. Socio-economic acceleration: per capita GDP PPP (Purchasing Power Parity).
2. Knowledge economy/Knowledge Socio-economic Index (KEI): based on the following four pillars:
 - (1) Socio-economic incentive and institutional regime,
 - (2) Education and human resources,
 - (3) The innovation system, and
 - (4) Information and communication technology.
3. Globalization: based on the KOF Index of Globalization, which measures the three ('plural') dimensions of globalization: Socio-economic, social, and political.
4. Global competitiveness/Global Competitiveness Index (GCI): measures a set of domestic institutions and policies for their respective global competitiveness: The index indicates 'national/domestic' competitiveness worldwide.
5. Terms of trade: It is calculated by dividing the value of exports by the value of imports, in multiplying the result by 100. Favorable term of trade is over 1, while unfavorable below 1.
6. Corruption/Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI): annually ranks countries by the perceived levels of corruption. The CPI ranks countries on a scale from 100 (very clean/transparent) to 0 (highly corrupt/non-transparent).
7. Urbanization (%): the measure is based on urban-rural dichotomy.
8. Types of political system/political freedom index: classified as "not free," "partly free," and "free": "not

- free” were coded as 1 (highly authoritarian), “partly free” as 2 (authoritarian), and “free” as 3 (democratic).
9. Military expenditure/defense spending: military expenditure as a percentage of GDP.
 10. Socio-economic freedom/Socio-economic Freedom Index: based on trade freedom, business freedom, financing freedom, and property rights.
 11. Oil (proven oil reserves/crude oil): based on countries with proven oil reserves.
 12. Foreign direct financing (FDI): net inflows (new financing inflows less disfinancing).
 13. Gross savings/ savings: measured by % of GDP: A measure that accounts for both private and public savings.
 14. Consumer spending/Utility: as % of GDP.
 15. Government spending: government expenditure as a percentage of GDP.
 16. Tax/Tax burden: measures corporate tax burden as a percentage of GDP.
 17. Domestic financing: domestic ‘private’ financing (physical financing) measured by % of GDP.
 18. Unemployment: measured by the percent of the labor force that is without jobs.

Result:

	Patterns					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
	Utility	Export	Oil	Savings	Govt Spending	Domestic Financing
Variables						
KEI	0.935	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Corruption	0.922	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
GCI	0.906	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Globalization	0.905	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Utility	0.8	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Urbanization	0.853	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Eco freedom	0.848	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
GDP/PPP	0.808	0.463	ns	ns	ns	ns
FDI	0.653	ns	ns	ns	-0.634	ns
Tax/GDP	ns	-0.914	ns	ns	ns	ns
Terms of Trade	ns	0.84	ns	ns	ns	ns

Oil	ns	ns	0.893	ns	ns	ns
Pol freedom	ns	ns	-0.718	ns	0.420	ns
Defense	ns	ns	0.484	ns	ns	0.471
Unemployment	ns	ns	ns	-0.901	ns	ns
Savings	ns	0.412	ns	0.688	ns	ns
Govt Spending	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Domestic Invest	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	-0.964
Eigen value %	-42.1	-13.7	-13.0	-7.8	-6.1	-5.7
ns: Non-Significant.						

Table 1 show six factors/patterns identified. Factor 1 documents nine variables (underlined) sufficient\ loaded: (1) KEI (knowledge economy), (2) Corruption, (3) GCI (Global Competitiveness Index), (4) Globalization (KOF index), (5) Utility (consumer spending), (6) Urbanization, (7) Eco freedom (Socio-economic freedom), (8) GDP/PPP (Socio-economic acceleration), and (9) FDI (foreign direct financing/inflow). The cluster of nine variables underlined goes together. Factor 1 is the only factor that sufficient\ loads Utility/consumer spending as well. Both Socio-economic acceleration and consumer spending are highly correlated each other, indicating the consumer-spending has positive effect on Socio-economic acceleration (GDP/PPP). Also the consumer spending is sufficient\ correlated with knowledge economy (KEI), corruption, global competitiveness (GCI), globalization, urbanization, and)',/inflow respectively. HLs means that the knowledge- economy which is based on information, communication, technology, Socio-economic innovation and incentive are very sufficient and positive ingredients facilitating consumer-spending/Utility, which turns out to have positive effect on Socio-economic acceleration as well. Corruption was found to negatively affect consumer spending as the corruption does distort market as well. When the market is distorted, it cannot facilitate consumer- spending. A high transparency associated with a lower corruption is one of the conditions required for a free market to be efficient as well. The lower the corruption, the more the Utility. In Socio-economics, a market is transparent if much is known by many about the availability of products, services or assets. Transparency can help foreign financing/inflow as well.)',/inflow were also found to have sufficient effect on Utility.)', /inflow by multinational corporations (MNCs) in host countries produce goods with a lower price as well as greater volume, which are favorable to the consumers. A high consumer spending is also positively associated with a high level of urbanization. Urbanization increases aggregate demands, which facilitate consumer spending. Both globalization measured by the KOF index and the global 'competiveness' measured by the GCI (Global Competitiveness Index) are not only highly correlated each other but also they are highly correlated with the Utility. The globalization by the KOF index does indicate 'international/external' world-wide interdependence and interconnectedness of a country while the global competitiveness measured by the GCI (Global Competitiveness Index) is based on

‘national/domestic’ institutional and policy/political areas that are compatible and competitive with the global standard. Thus the global competitiveness assesses the competitiveness of ‘national/domestic’ competitiveness worldwide: It is a set of institutions, policies, and factors that determine the level of productivity and prosperity of a country. These ‘two’ levels of globalization, international/external and national/ domestic, were found to have positive effects on Utility. They are mutual and sufficient\ correlated each other. These two globalizations have also provided an opportunity to focus global attention on previously-neglected issues such as corruption (lack of transparency). Socio-economic freedom has positive effect on Utility, indicating that a free market- economy does facilitate the consumer spending. Factor 1 is labeled as a “Utility-driven economy.” Countries in Asia classified as the most/least Utility-driven economy.

With the following formula: [factor loading (variable) x z-score (variable)]. MOST: Singapore, Japan, UAE, Israel, South Korea; LEAST: Nepal, Bangladesh, Tajikistan, Pakistan, Vietnam. Factor 2 has four variables loaded: (1) Tax (tax burden), (2) Terms of trade, (3) GDP/PPP (Socio-economic acceleration), and (4) Savings (gross savings). Factor 2, like Factor 1 (Utility-driven economy), was found to load GDP/PPP (Socio-economic acceleration) but not Consumer (consumer spending) variables. None of the four variables, including the Socio-economic acceleration, was found to sufficient\ correlate with the consumer spending. Tax as measured by the % corporate tax of GDP indicates that a high taxation has negative effect on Socio-economic acceleration. A high taxation also is associated with unfavorable terms of trade. In Factor 2, both the taxation and the terms of trade were found sufficient in affect Socio-economic acceleration: High taxation imposed on corporate was found to result in an unfavorable terms of trade, all of which have negative effects on Socio-economic acceleration. Unfavorable terms of trade are clearly detrimental to the Socio-economic acceleration. Yet the savings turn out to have a positive effect on Socio-economic acceleration. Both high taxation and unfavorable terms of trade lower the savings, which otherwise would have a positive effect on Socio-economic acceleration. A lower savings mean a lower Socio-economic acceleration. Tax burden imposed on corporate affects not only the terms of trade but also savings. Although taxation, terms of trade, and savings were found sufficient determinants of Socio-economic acceleration, none of the three variables was found to affect Utility. Unlike Factor 1 (Utility-driven economy), Factor 2 indicates that Socio-economic acceleration is affected not by Utility but trade (export), savings, and taxation. Factor 2 is labeled as an “export-led economy” pattern. Countries most/least classified as export-led acceleration economy in Asia are: MOST: Qatar, Kuwait, Macau, Singapore, Hong Kong; LEAST: Pakistan, Japan, India, Bhutan, and Bangladesh. (Note: One notable finding here is that Japan, classified already as one of the most ‘Utility –driven economy’ countries (Factor 1), was found to be one of the least countries classified as the ‘export-led economy.’ This means Japan must have experienced a low Socio-economic acceleration, unfavorable term of trade, low savings, and yet high corporate taxation during the period (2012-16) covered in this study. Although Japan was classified as one of the most ‘Utility- driven economy’ (Factor 1), yet it was classified as one of the least ‘export -led economy’ countries. This means Japan’s

Socio-economic acceleration is still based more on the Utility-driven rather than on the export-led model). Factor 3 loads three variables: Oil (oil richness/resources), Poli freedom (political freedom), and Defense (defense spending). None of the three variables was found to affect Socio-economic acceleration or consumer spending. Oil resource and defense spending are closely associated with each other. This means that the oil-rich/resource countries in Asia are able to spend a larger amount of money in military expenditures than oil-depleted counterparts. Those oil-rich countries are also politically less democratic: They are classified as authoritarian political system. Neither the oil –richness nor the defense spending was found to affect Socio-economic acceleration as well as consumer spending. Oil, politics/political freedom, and defense spending were found to have no significant effects on Socio-economic acceleration.

Eco free	0.074	1.78	0.182								
PPP	0	3.283	0.07								
FDI	0	0.149	0.7								
Const	-11.537	5.641	0.018								
Pattern 4				Pattern 5				Pattern 6			
Savings				Government Spending				Domestic Financing			
	B	Wald	Sig		B	Wald	Sig		B	Wald	Sig
Variables		o		Variables		o		Variables		o	
Unemp	-0.002	0.579	0.447	FDI	0	1.581	0.209	Defense	0.052	12.144	0
Savings	0.071	9.893	0.002	Pol free	-1.148	21.412	0	Domestic invest	0.033	1.572	0.21
Const	-2.29	11.1	0.001	Gov spending	0	0.002	0.966	Const	-2.989	15.751	0
				Const	1.359	5.501	0.019				

Singularity to Asian Economy

Table 2 presents the Logistic Regression Analysis (SPSS) of the likelihood/probability of being ‘unique’ to Asian economy. The table is based on a dichotomous variable, in which 222 countries in the world are divided into two groups: countries in Asia (52) are coded as 1, while the rest of the world countries as 0. The dichotomous variable is treated as dependent variable. The uniqueness to Asian economies is based on each and every of the six patterns of the Socio-economic acceleration as shown in Table 1. Those variables that significant\ load on each factor/pattern were treated as independent variables. And the Waldo statistics (coefficient/standard error) in Table 2 indicates the level of significance of each independent variable in contributing to the likelihood of the uniqueness. The variables significant at 0.05 level were underlined. Pattern 1 (Utility-driven economy) in Table 2 shows that Corruption, GCI (global competitiveness index), and Global (globalization/KOF index) were each found to significant\ different Late in the Utility-driven economy between Asia and the rest of world. Corruption and its regression coefficient (-.1.712) indicates that the Corruption Perception Index/CPI is lower in Asia than the rest of the world: The lower the index, the more corrupt, and vice versa. HLs means that Asian ‘economies’ is perceived as having a higher corruption than the rest of the world, indicating that corruption problems are high in many countries Asia. A high corruption distorts market which can have a negative effect on consumer-spending as well. Yet GCI (Global Competiveness Index) and its regression coefficient (4.274) is very strong for Asian economies, which is well contrasted with the rest of the world. Despite a high ‘national/domestic’ global competitiveness worldwide in Asian economies, ‘international/external’ globalization is still relatively low in comparison with the rest of the world. The regression coefficient (-.136) of Global (globalization) shows that Asian economies experience a lower level of ‘international/external’ globalization than the rest of the world: A low globalization was found to have a significant effect on the likelihood of Asian economy. Despite a low ‘international/external’ globalization,’ Asian countries have a strong ‘national/domestic’ global competitiveness worldwide as measured by GCI, which was found to have significant effect on the likelihood of Asian economy. In Pattern 2 (export-led economy)/Table 2, Savings and its regression coefficient .110 indicates that a high savings were found to have significant effect\ on the likelihood of Asian economies. Asian economy is rather ‘unique’ in that a large savings play an important role in contributing to Socio-economic acceleration as was shown in the ‘export led acceleration economy’ pattern in Asia. In Pattern 3 (oil-based economy)/Table 2, Pol free (political freedom) was found significant along with its large regression coefficient (-.844). This means that a significant effect of the politics on the ‘trade-o’ between oil-resources and defense spending are conspicuous in Asia, which different Asia from the rest of the world: The effect of 'politics' on the oil-based economy is significant in the Asian economy. Authoritarian political system is more likely to be able to ‘utilize’ the oil-richness for a large defense spending purpose than democratic counterparts in Asia. Yet none of the two ‘nonpolitical ‘variables of the oil-based economy, defense spending and oil resources, was found to have significant effects on the likelihood of being Asian economy only. This means that the positive effect of the oil-resources on the defense spending as was addressed in the patterning of the oil-rich economy (see Table 1/Pattern 3) is rather universal, Asia or the

rest of the world. Yet in the Asian economy, politics was found to have significant effect on the oil-based economy, which is different from the rest of the world. In Pattern 4 (saving-based economy)/Table 2, Savings and its regression coefficient (.071) indicate that a high savings was found to have significant effect on the likelihood of Asian economy. The savings was also found significant in the export-led economy (Pattern 2/Table 2). Yet the savings in Pattern 4 indicates an ‘employment-based savings’ as was previously discussed. Despite its significant effect on Socio-economic acceleration, the employment-based savings turn out to have significant effect on the likelihood of Asian economy. This means the savings, whether in the export-led economy or in the employment

Conclusion

Patterns of Asian Socio-economic acceleration were found diverse, yet there were some features ‘unique’ to the Asian economies as well, which is distinguished from the rest of the world. Six patterns of Asian Socio-economic acceleration were Identified Utility-driven; export-led; oil rich/resources; employment saving-based; government spending; and domestic financing. The Utility-driven economy is the most predominant pattern of Asian Socio-economic acceleration. Both the Utility-driven and the export-led economies were found significant in positively affect in Socio-economic acceleration, while oil-resources, employment based-savings, government spending, and domestic financing not. In its effects on Socio-economic acceleration, the Utility driven economy is not unit dimensional solely based on the consumer spending. It was found multidimensional beyond a singular consumer spending variable. The Utility is significant\ affected by knowledge economy, globalization, global competitiveness, Socio-economic freedom/free market system, urbanization, a low corruption (a high transparency), and foreign direct financing (FDI) inflows. And the knowledge-economy based on innovation, information, and technology, was found the strongest of all in increasing consumer spending. The six patterns of Socio-economic acceleration found in Asia are commonly shared with the rest of the world economy as well, yet there were some ‘uniqueness’ to the Asian economy, which features as follows: (1) high savings; (2) a large defense spending affected by oil-richness as well as by politics (authoritarian government) (3) a high ‘national/domestic’ global competitiveness worldwide despite a relatively low ‘international/ external’ globalization. (4) A high corruption which distorts market.

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Please follow:

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Authors name and details:

Trisha Rahman

School of Business Management and Economics

Liaoning University of Technology

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